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Designing Sustainable Blended Courses and Programmes Beyond Borders Using the European Maturity Model for Blended Education

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EMBED+ CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS

A layered model of blended education

THREE PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES

1. CONSTRUCTIVE ALIGNMENT

Coherence between learning outcomes, activities and assessment across online and face-to-face learning.

2. PROGRESSIVE SCAFFOLDING

Gradual shift from structured support towards increasing learner autonomy.

3. ITERATIVE, INFORMED (RE)DESIGN

Continuous evaluation and refinement informed by evidence and feedback.

Maturity ≠ Quality

Maturity is the **ability** of a (blended) course or program to **evolve** over time **and adapt in response to** challenges, feedback, and experiences.

Quality refers to how well a (blended) course or program **performs** in delivering its **intended outcomes**, meeting **standards** of excellence.

EMBED+ MATURITY FRAMEWORK

How blended practices evolve

THREE MATURITY FEATURES

1. DESIGN & DEVELOPMENT

Pedagogically grounded design that is aligned, implemented and iteratively improved.

2. INFORMATION-DRIVEN CHANGE

Systematic use of information to generate insights and inform decisions for improvement.

3. ADAPTIVITY

Intentional adjustment to learner diversity and context within ethical and legal boundaries.

FOUR MATURITY STAGES

1. AD HOC

Isolated

Uncoordinated and implicit practices.

2. DELIBERATE

Intentional

Designed with goals in mind; limited coordination and insight.

3. RESPONSIVE

Iterative

Evidence-informed adjustments to strengthen alignment and responsiveness.

4. EMBEDDED

Sustained

Integrated, coherent and continuously improved.

Maturity is the developmental progression of blended practices across course, programme and organisation levels.

COURSE LEVEL

Teaching & learning
in the course

Proportioning & sequencing

Learning technologies & media

Blended interaction

Learner guidance

Learning workload

PROGRAMME LEVEL

Coherence across
courses

Curriculum coherence

Learning technologies & media

Learning workload

Learner guidance

Capacity development

ORGANISATION LEVEL

Enabling blended
education

Strategy & policy

Governance & finances

Support ecosystem

Capacity development

Technology ecosystem

Quality culture

DIMENSION 3 – SUPPORT ECOSYSTEM (enables blended practices in real time)

An integrated and coordinated system of pedagogical, technical, instructional, and organisational support services that enables staff and learners to design, implement, and sustain blended practices. It focuses on practice-oriented support and task-based collaboration for blended teaching and learning (BT&L), ensuring context-sensitive assistance across stakeholder groups.

Feature	Ad hoc	Deliberate	Responsive	Embedded
Design & development	Support for BT&L is fragmented and reactive; support is limited to isolated course-level interventions without systematic alignment to programme-level blended design.	Core support services for blended education are available (e.g., pedagogical advice, instructional design support); initial coordination across courses exists but remains inconsistent and weakly aligned with programme-level blended design needs.	Coordinated support integrates pedagogical and instructional expertise to support design, delivery, and improvement of blended courses and programmes across online and face-to-face modalities; structured collaboration supports consistent implementation across organisational units.	Organisation-wide support ecosystem is embedded in blended education practice; support is fully integrated into course and programme design processes, ensuring coherent, scalable, and sustainable implementation of BT&L across the organisation.
Information-driven change	No systematic insight into how support for BT&L is used or how it influences course design and delivery.	Feedback on support services is collected but fragmented and weakly linked to improvements in BT&L practice.	Evidence on support use and effectiveness is systematically used to improve blended course design support, instructional processes, and programme-level implementation.	Longitudinal evidence on support for BT&L is systematically used to optimise organisational support systems and ensure alignment with blended education goals across all levels.
Adaptivity	Support for BT&L is generic and not adapted to modality-specific needs (online, face-to-face, or integrated course design); support is reactive rather than proactive.	Support services show limited differentiation by role, discipline, or blended course design needs; adaptivity is inconsistent and depends on local initiative.	Support is tailored to roles, disciplines, and blended course/programme contexts; adaptivity ensures alignment between pedagogical intent and practical implementation across modalities.	The support ecosystem dynamically adapts to evolving BT&L practices, ensuring sustainable, inclusive, and context-responsive implementation support across the organisation.

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